

Geographic Analytics for Exploring Spatial Patterns between Air Pollution and Community-Acquired Pneumonia Severity in Germany: A Proof-of-Concept

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Abstract.

Community-acquired pneumonia (CAP) is associated with substantial incidence and mortality in Germany. Previous research has predominantly focused on short-term, temporal associations between weather, air pollution, and CAP hospitalizations. In contrast, this study adopts a spatial perspective and explores whether long-term air-pollution exposure is associated with regional patterns of CAP severity. We present a Geographic Analytics workflow that integrates interpolated long-term exposure surfaces with region-level severity indicators derived from hospitalization data across Germany. The visualization approach enables exploratory spatial screening of potential co-occurrence patterns. By shifting from temporal prediction to spatial assessment, the proposed framework aims to support public health authorities, healthcare researchers, and health insurance providers in identifying candidate areas for geographically targeted prevention and resource prioritization.

Submission type. analysis; case study; methodology/workflow

BoK Concepts. [CV6-6] Spatial thinking; [AM4-3] Overlay

Keywords. Geographic Analytics, community-acquired pneumonia, visualization, air pollution, spatial decision support, Germany

1 Introduction

Community-acquired pneumonia (CAP) is associated with high burden and adverse outcomes in Germany. In a population-based analysis, overall CAP incidence was estimated at 1,054 cases per 100,000 person-years, with hospitalized CAP mortality of 22.9% at 30

days (Theilacker et al., 2021). Routine-care evidence similarly indicates frequent hospitalization and substantial short-term mortality, and highlights immunosuppression as a key vulnerability factor (Reichel et al., 2024). These findings support the relevance of decision-oriented, spatially explicit approaches that can help localize candidate areas for targeted follow-up e.g., surveillance prioritization, prevention focus, or analytic deep dives with richer covariates.

Evidence linking air quality to CAP frequently focuses on short-term associations with hospitalization timing, typically using time-series or case-crossover designs (Yee et al., 2021). Although long-term approaches exist, such as Neupane et al. (2010) using one to two years of residential exposure before CAP hospitalization, this time window reflects only a small part of cumulative exposure compared with life-course pollutant burden.

The Geographic Analytics contribution presented here therefore differs by using a visual, map-centred representation of longer-term exposure to support spatial screening rather than temporal prediction of admission dates. The goal is to support authorities, healthcare researchers, and health insurance providers in decisions on geographically targeted prevention and prioritisation, thereby contributing to improved public health.

2 Approach: Geographic Analytics

Geographic Analytics is applied as an analysis workflow that transforms heterogeneous environmental and health data into layered geovisual representations to support decision-relevant interpretation. Two data streams are integrated for Germany from the years 2010–2016:

- **CAP severity (region-based):** CAP severity quantified using CRB-65 and aggregated to two-digit postal code regions. CRB-65 is a clinical severity

Figure 1. Geographic Analytics overlay design (example for ozone): regional CRB-65 severity indicator (left), interpolated ozone exposure surface (centre), and combined visualization (right).

score based on confusion, respiratory rate, blood pressure, and age ≥ 65 years, where higher scores indicate greater severity.

- **Air quality:** station measurements for CO, NO₂, O₃, PM₁₀, SO₂ aggregated to long-term summaries and interpolated to continuous exposure surfaces via IDW (inverse distance weighting).

The Geographic Analytics workflow comprises: (i) temporal harmonization and cleaning; (ii) spatial allocation of monitoring stations to the analysis extent; (iii) exposure-surface creation via IDW; (iv) layered mapping that combines grayscale pollutant rasters with semi-transparent severity polygons; (v) exploratory visual analysis of map overlays to identify candidate spatial co-occurrence patterns Figure 1 illustrates the overlay concept used for screening (shown for ozone as an example); and (vi) an exploratory statistical cross-check using bivariate Moran's I, computed from region-level CRB-65 indicators and zonal summaries of interpolated pollutant surfaces, to assess whether visually suggested patterns are reflected in global spatial association.

3 Limitations

The contribution is positioned as a proof-of-concept for Geographic Analytics, exploring geo-correlations in healthcare rather than providing confirmatory epidemiological evidence. Statistical power and interpretability are constrained by limited case numbers and coarse spatial aggregation (two-digit postal codes), which reduces sensitivity to local variation and limits subgroup analyses. Severity measurement via CRB-65 includes age (≥ 65 years), which can bias regional comparisons if age structures differ. Exposure surfaces derived from unevenly distributed monitoring stations introduce interpolation uncertainty, and potential confounders (e.g., meteorology, socioeconomic variables, comorbidity profiles) are not modelled.

Methodologically, the analysis relies on inverse distance weighting (IDW) with a fixed power parameter ($p = 2$), without formal sensitivity analysis or comparison to alternative interpolation methods. The statistical assessment is limited to global bivariate Moran's I, which may not detect localized spatial clustering; local indicators of spatial association (e.g., LISA) are not applied during this pilot stage. As a result, visually identified regional patterns cannot yet be formally validated as statistically significant clusters within this framework.

sectionResults and outlook The overlays indicate localized co-occurrence patterns between higher O₃ and NO₂ exposure surfaces and higher regional severity indicators, whereas PM₁₀, SO₂, and CO show less consistent correspondence at the two-digit postal code resolution. Complementary global Moran's I remains close to zero across pollutants, indicating weak global spatial association at the available granularity.

This apparent discrepancy suggests that any relationships may be spatially heterogeneous and confined to specific regions rather than forming a consistent nationwide pattern. As global Moran's I captures only overall spatial dependence, localized co-occurrence patterns identified through visual inspection are not necessarily reflected in the global statistic.

Overall, the results support Geographic Analytics as a screening step to identify regions where follow-up with finer patient geocoding, additional covariates, and higher-resolution exposure data is most warranted; at the same time, the approach shows potential to differentiate pollutant-specific spatial signals in relation to pneumonia severity.

Further work is encouraged using larger datasets with finer geocoding and patient attributes. On the environmental side, integrating satellite-derived air-quality products with ground-based monitoring is expected to improve spatial completeness and resolution. Together, these steps can strengthen Geographic Analytics as a reproducible pathway from spatial data to decision-oriented screening and subsequent confirmatory analysis. In application,

the workflow can support authorities in prioritising geographically targeted air-quality and prevention measures, enable healthcare research entities to prioritise candidate regions and factors for higher-resolution studies, and assist health insurance providers in designing and evaluating place-based preventive interventions for populations at elevated risk.

3.1 Data and Software Availability

Ground-based air quality measurements (CO, NO₂, O₃, PM₁₀, SO₂) were obtained from the German Environment Agency (Umweltbundesamt, UBA) monitoring network and accessed via the UBA air data portal (<https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/daten/luft/luftdaten>). While CAP registry data contain sensitive health information and are subject to ethical and contractual access restrictions. Where individual-level CAP data cannot be shared, aggregated exemplars or synthetic data may support partial reproducibility on request.

Declaration of Generative AI in writing

The authors declare that Generative AI tools have been used in the preparation of this manuscript. Specifically, AI tools were utilized for language editing, improving grammar, and sentence structure but not for generating scientific content, research data, or substantive conclusions. All intellectual and creative work, including the analysis and interpretation of data, is original and has been conducted by the authors with human oversight and accountability.

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